

CRYSTALLINE STRUCTURE OF $M^I_2M^{II}P_2O_7$ (M^I – Li, Na; M^{II} – Mn, Co, Ni) COMPOUNDS AND GROWING OF THEIR SINGLE CRYSTALS

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Abstract. *Complex phosphates containing diphosphate ions have been identified in the fluxes of $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-Mn_2O_3-MF$ and $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-M^{II}O-MF$ systems (where M^I – Li, Na; M^{II} – Ni, Co) for the first time. Optimum conditions for the growing of single crystals of $Li_2MnP_2O_7$, $Na_2MnP_2O_7$, $Na_2NiP_2O_7$ and $Na_2CoP_2O_7$ compounds have been determined.*

The effect of fluoride ions on the interactions in the fluxes of $M_2O-P_2O_5-Me_xO_y-MF$ systems (where, Me_xO_y – Mn_2O_3 , NiO and CoO) has been studied in two sets: with 10 and 20% (wt.) of respective alkali metal fluorides. The solubility and interaction of d-metal oxides in the systems have been studied at a temperature ranging from 750 to 950 °C. Mole ratios of $M_2O:P_2O_5$ have been changed over the 0.5 to 2.0 range and oxide content in the original fluxes of the studied system – over the 6.0-37.0% wt. range.

In order to study single crystals of synthesized phosphates, a complete X-ray diffraction analysis has been performed, which resulted in the establishment and refinement of lattice parameters of $Na_2MnP_2O_7$ and $Na_2CoP_2O_7$.

To produce single crystals of double phosphates, the crystallization procedure has been conducted under temperature gradient of 10-15 °C/cm at 680-970 °C and

cooling rate 2-5 degrees/h; the crucible volume was 100-150 mL, flux system weight – 40-60 gr. X-ray diffraction analysis of single crystals of $\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Na}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Na}_2\text{NiP}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$ have been conducted using Siemens P3/PC diffractometer under molybdenum radiation with graphite monochromator.

The synthesized compounds have been studied using the following techniques: RSA, DTA, IR- and EPR-spectroscopy; the relation between conductivity and temperature was established for the obtained phosphates. Based on the findings from conducted research, a set of physicochemical properties has been proposed for the synthesized compounds, which can be utilized in the development of functional materials.

Keywords: *double phosphates, DTA, XRD, flux crystallization, XRF.*

INTRODUCTION. Much recent research has been focused on the synthesis and properties of alkali and 3d-metal phosphates, in particular manganese, cobalt and nickel [1-3]. Scientists have achieved considerable success in the field of inorganic chemistry of molten phosphates and synthesis of single and double phosphates of alkali and multivalent metals [4, 5]. Several new types of phosphate compounds have been produced, mainly by the solid-phase synthesis and synthesis from polyphosphoric acids [6]. The data on the synthesis of some bianionic double phosphates of manganese (II) and (III), cobalt and nickel from solutions of polyphosphoric acids have been published [7, 8]. The interaction of NiO oxide in the fluxes of $\text{M}^{\text{I}}_2\text{O}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5$ -MF systems (where, $\text{M}^{\text{I}} - \text{Li, Na, K}$) has been studied along with investigation of crystallization range of compounds in such fluxes [9, 10]. Still, there are many open issues associated with the solubility and interaction of alkali metal fluorides in $\text{M}^{\text{I}}_2\text{O}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5-\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_3$ -MF and $\text{M}^{\text{I}}_2\text{O}-\text{P}_2\text{O}_5-\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{O}$ -MF fluxes. Tailor-made synthesis of phosphate compounds with various characteristics gives an impetus to the detailed study of their physicochemical properties and structure, which will be further used in new technologies and investigations [11].

Thus, the investigation of phase formation and crystallization conditions, determination of double phosphate formation domains in the fluxes of fluoride phosphate systems, exploration of their crystalline structure and properties are highly topical tasks and long-range objectives for the development of new compounds synthesis.

The purpose of this study is to determine optimum conditions for the synthesis of a series of double diphosphates in the fluxes of $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-Mn_2O_3-MF$ and $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-M^{II}O-MF$ systems (where, $M^I - Li, Na, K$; $M^{II} - Mn, Ni, Co$) and investigate their physicochemical properties and composition [12].

Experimental. Double diphosphates $Li_2MnP_2O_7$, $Na_2NiP_2O_7$, $Na_2MnP_2O_7$ and $Na_2CoP_2O_7$ have been synthesized in the studies of interaction and solubility of NiO , CoO and Mn_2O_3 oxides in the fluxes of $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-Mn_2O_3-MF$ and $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-M^{II}O-MF$ systems (where, $M^I - Li, Na$; $M^{II} - Ni, Co$). The crystalline structure of $M^I_2M^{II}P_2O_7$ -type compounds has been determined using total X-ray diffraction method.

The effect of fluoride ions on the interactions in the fluxes of $M_2O-P_2O_5-Me_xO_y-MF$ systems (where, $Me_xO_y - Mn_2O_3, NiO$ and CoO) has been studied in two sets: with 10 and 20% (wt.) of respective alkali metal fluorides. The solubility and interaction of d-metal oxides in the systems have been studied at a temperature ranging from 750 to 950 °C. Mole ratios of $M_2O:P_2O_5$ have been changed over the 0.5 to 2.0 range and oxide content in the original fluxes of the studied system – over the 6.0-37.0% wt. range.

Prepared mixtures of original substances with specified $M_2O:P_2O_5$ mole ratios have been grinded up with d-metal oxides and heated thoroughly in platinum crucibles on a fire of gas-heated soldering iron until extraction of ammonia and water. The fluxes have been homogenized at 750-920° C for 2-3 hours with subsequent addition of calculated quantities of alkali metal fluorides, then mixed and homogenized at temperatures elevated by 30-50 °C.

Following saturation of metal oxide, the fluxes were mixed and kept for 3-4 hours, along with determination of the temperature of solid phase crystallization start. The samples of liquid equilibrium phases of the fluxes of $M_2O-P_2O_5-Me_xO_y-MF$ systems (where, $Me_xO_y - Mn_2O_3, NiO$ and CoO) have been drawn at respective temperatures and analyzed for d-metal oxides content. Then, the temperature was elevated by 20-30 °C and fluxes were crystallized out at 970-680 °C. Obtained crystals were washed of the flux with diluted solutions of mineral acids, rinsed thoroughly with distilled water and dried.

To produce single crystals of double phosphates, the crystallization procedure has been conducted under temperature gradient of 10-15 °C/cm at 680-970 °C and cooling rate 2-5 degrees/h; the crucible volume was 100-150 mL, flux system weight – 40-60 gr. The optimum conditions for the growing of single crystals of the specified compounds are given in the Table 1.

Table 1. Conditions for the formation of double phosphates in systems $M_2O-P_2O_5-Mn_2O_3$; $M_2O-P_2O_5-Mn_2O_3-MF$ and $M_2O-P_2O_5-M^{II}O-MF$

Formula compound	Mole relations $M_2O:P_2O_5$			Crystallization interval, C°	Syng., space group, lattice parameters, (Å)	Color	$T_{melt.}$, C°
	- MF	(10%) MF	(20%) MF				
$Li_2MnP_2O_7$	-	-	0,5-0,62	830-700	Mon. $P2_1/a$; a=9,883, b=9,800, c=11,147, $\beta=102,14^\circ$	Dark-brown	985
$Na_2MnP_2O_7$	0,91-1,2	0,76-1,4	0,5-0,76	920-750	Tr. $P\bar{1}$; a=6,548, b=9,537, c=11,071,	Dark-red	720

					$\alpha=64,62^\circ$, $\beta=79,79^\circ$, $\gamma=73,13^\circ$		
$\text{Na}_2\text{NiP}_2\text{O}_7$	0,8- 1,2	0,58- 1,0	1,0-1,6	920-750	Tr. P1; a=6,389, b=9,327, c=10,862, $\alpha=64,62^\circ$, $\beta=80,15^\circ$, $\gamma=73,60^\circ$	Red	765
$\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$	0,8- 1,2	0,50- 0,66	0,50- 0,91	900-700	Tr. P1; a=6,380, b=9,371, c=10,940, $\alpha=64,65^\circ$, $\beta=86,15^\circ$, $\gamma=73,16^\circ$	Yellow	730

Solid phases have been identified using quantitative chemical and physicochemical analytical methods, namely: XRD, DTA, IR- and EPR-spectroscopy, along with the determination of relationship between conductivity and temperature.

Results and Discussion. X-ray diffraction analysis of single crystals of $\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Na}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$, $\text{Na}_2\text{NiP}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$ have been conducted using Siemens P3/PC diffractometer under molybdenum radiation with graphite monochromator.

Unlike two other double diphosphates, the structure of $\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$ belongs to monoclinic crystal system, space group $\text{P}2_1/\text{a}$, lattice parameters: $a=9.883(2)$, $b=9.800(2)$, $c=11.147(2)$ Å; $\beta=102.44^\circ$; $Z=6$, $\rho_{\text{calc.}}=2.414$ g/cm³.

The integral intensities have been measured using $2\theta:\theta$ method over the range of angles $7.48^\circ < 2\theta < 50.10^\circ$ with variable scanning speed of 2-28 °/min. As a result

of X-ray diffraction analysis, 1625 reflections (within $-1 \leq h \leq 11$, $0 \leq k \leq 11$, $0 \leq l \leq 13$) have been obtained, of which 1267 independent reflections with $I > 2\sigma(I)$ have been used for calculations. Adjustments for polarization and Lorentz factor correction have been applied to the dataset. The structure has been calculated using heavy atom method; the correction has been performed using full-matrix least-squares method with anisotropic approximation for all of the atoms. The final value of the divergence factor was $R_w = 0.048$.

Fig. 1. Projection of $\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$ on yz plane

Fig.1 shows the projection of $\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$ structure on yz plane. The structure comprises two types of manganese polyhedra: octahedra $\text{Mn}(1)\text{O}_6$ and pentagons $\text{Mn}(2)\text{O}_5$, sharing common edge $\text{O}(1)-\text{O}(12)$. The length of Mn-O bonds in the octahedron and pentagon lie within 2.109-2.294 Å and 2.113-2.240 Å, respectively (see Table). The $\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$ structure contains two differing by crystallographic form diphosphate groups of $[\text{P}_2\text{O}_7]$ with bridges $\text{P}(1)-\text{O}(4)-\text{P}(2)$ ($\angle 131.2^\circ$) and $\text{P}(3)-\text{O}(11)-\text{P}(4)$ ($\angle 128.2^\circ$). The bonds in P-O-P bridge are nearly equal and make 3.215 Å та 3.213 Å, respectively.

Two diphosphate groups, P(1)P(2)O₇ and P(3)P(4)O₇, contract Mn(1)O₆ and Mn(2)O₅ polyhedra (see Fig. 1) with their terminal atoms of oxygen and in such a way stiffen the framework of Li₂MnP₂O₇ structure. Interestingly, atoms of lithium in the structure have different coordination numbers and form Li(2), Li(3) tetrahedra (Li-O distances: 1.993-2.331 Å) and Li(1), Li(4) pentagons (Li-O distances: Li-O 1.943-2.246 Å), respectively. In Li₂MnP₂O₇ structure, the channels filled with lithium polyhedra run in the voids between manganese and phosphorus polyhedra, and along the *oy* axis.

The isostructurality of Na₂MnP₂O₇ and Na₂CoP₂O₇ double phosphates has been determined with X-ray diffraction method. According to their structure, the compounds belong to triclinic crystal system, space group P $\bar{1}$. The data obtained in the XRD-analysis for the specified double diphosphates differ from those mentioned in the literature [13] for crystalline lattices of compounds with noncentrosymmetric space group P1.

The structure of Na₂M^{II}P₂O₇ (where, M^{II} – Mn, Co) is based on the framework, which consists of distorted [M^{II}O₆] octahedral and binding them [P₂O₇] diphosphate groups (Fig. 2). Crystallographically non-equivalent Mn(1)O₆ and Mn(2)O₆ polyhedra are joined pairwise via the common atom of oxygen O(10) (see Table 4). This group is further reinforced by the edges of phosphate tetrahedra O(3)-O(1) and O(13)-O(12), which contract manganese polyhedra. The length of Mn-O bonds in Mn(1) and Mn(2) octahedra fall within 2.126-2.261 Å and 2.061-2.406 Å, respectively. [CoO₆] polyhedra demonstrate slightly shorter length of bonds between cobalt and oxygen atoms. In particular, the length of Co-O bonds in Co(1) and Co(2) octahedra fall within 2.055-2.165 Å and 2.006-2.310 Å.

Fig. 2. Projection of Na₂MnIP₂O₇ structure on yz plane

Interpretation and refinement of the structures have been performed using SHELX-97 applications [12]. The presence of slightly prolonged Mn(2)-O(9) bond in the structure of Na₂MnP₂O₇ compound is likely to cause the dark-cherry color of Na₂MnP₂O₇ single crystals. It is evident that the coordination number 5 is more characteristic for Mn(2) atom comparing to Co(2) atom, and this determines the color of Na₂MnP₂O₇ compound. Two crystallographically non-equivalent [P₂O₇] groups in the structure of Na₂MnP₂O₇ contain P(1)-O(4)-P(2) ($\angle$ 126.7°) and P(3)-O(11)-P(4) ($\angle$ 132.6°) bridge fragments. The length of P(1)-O(4) and P(2)-O(4) bonds in the first diphosphate group is 1.621 Å and 1.636 Å, respectively. The length of bonds in P(1)-O(4)-P(2) group is slightly bigger (Δ 0.069 Å) than the length of respective bridge fragment of the second diphosphate group and makes 3.267 Å.

The length of P-O bonds in phosphorus-oxygen tetrahedra of two [P₂O₇] groups falls within rather wide interval: 1.495-1.636 Å. In this setting, the length of P-O bonds in P(3)P(4)O₇ group is significantly shorter than in the P(1)P(2)O₇ group, which is attributable to the location between Mn(1)O₆ and Mn(2)O₆ polyhedra and their contraction along the *oz* axis.

Similar to the crystalline structure of double diphosphate of manganese, the structure of $\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$ comprises two crystallographically non-equivalent diphosphate groups, $\text{P}(1)\text{P}(2)\text{O}_7$ and $\text{P}(3)\text{P}(4)\text{O}_7$. The angles formed by the atoms of phosphorus with bridge oxygen atoms are nearly comparable to the angles at bridge fragments of the mentioned above phosphate - $\angle \text{P}(1)\text{-O}(4)\text{-P}(2)$ (125.43°) and $\angle \text{P}(3)\text{-O}(11)\text{-P}(4)$ (132.73°). The lengths of bonds between respective atoms of phosphorus and oxygen in $[\text{PO}_4]$ polyhedra of the given structures are closely equal. This again is indicative of the isostructurality of the synthesized double diphosphates. The presence of statistically irregular Na(3), Na(4) and Na(4A) atoms in the voids of $\text{M}_2\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{P}_2\text{O}_7$ structure is responsible for some physical properties of the synthesized double phosphates, in particular, higher ionic conductivity.

To prove the presence of Mn^{2+} in the composition of double phosphates with different phosphate anions, the EPR-spectra have been studied on polycrystalline samples drawn at 23°C using „PS 100-X,, spectrometer. The spectral lines demonstrate characteristic broadening; the calculated values for g-tensor fall within 1.98-1.99. The resulting spectra of electron paramagnetic resonance for the synthesized double phosphates of manganese (II) are typical and characteristic [14].

The isostructurality of complex double diphosphates $\text{Na}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$ is further supported by the data of infrared spectroscopy (Table 2). Infrared spectra of the compounds have been studied at UR-20 and UR-10 (Carl Zeiss) spectrophotometers using KBr tablets.

Table 2. Infrared spectrum of double phosphates (cm^{-1})

Ingning frequencies	Formula compound			
	$\text{Na}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$	$\text{Na}_2\text{CoP}_2\text{O}_7$	$\text{Na}_2\text{NiP}_2\text{O}_7$	$\text{Li}_2\text{MnP}_2\text{O}_7$
τ (PO_3) fluct. lattice	490 sh.	490 sh.	465 sh. 495 str.	450 w.
δ_s P–O	515 str.	540 str. 570 str.	545 str. 575 str.	520 w. 550 w.

δ_{as} + ν MO			590 sh. 615 sh.	580 str. 615 sh. 650 sh.
ν_s P–O–P	740 w.	740 sh.	730 str.	770 str.
ν_{as} P–O–P	910 str.	910 str.	880 str. 920 str. 960 str.	950 str.
ν_s PO ₂	1050 sh. 1100 sh. 1110 v.str.	1020 sh. 1100 str.	1005 str. 1050 str.	1010 str. 1120 str.
ν_{as} PO ₂	1140 sh. 1180 sh. 1210 sh.	1180 sh. 1210 sh.	1160 v.str. 1210 str.	1210 str.

The basis of Na₂NiP₂O₇ structure is formed by the framework of distorted NiO₆ octahedra bound to diphosphate groups (Fig 3). Crystallographically independent atoms of nickel are joined pairwise via the common O(14) atom. This fragment is further reinforced by the edges of phosphate tetrahedra O(5)-O(7) and O(8)-O(9), which contract polyhedra on nickel atoms. Mean Ni-O distances are 2.065 and 2.086 Å for Ni(1) and Ni(2) atoms, respectively. Only terminal oxygen atoms of phosphate anion are involved in the coordination. The bonds formed by bridge atom of oxygen demonstrate the biggest length. O(12), positioned on the edge coordinating the diphosphate group to cation, is located on the longer distance from Ni (1) atom.

Fig. 3. Projection of $\text{Na}_2\text{NiP}_2\text{O}_7$ Projection of yz plane

The typical structure of diphosphate groups is preserved; mean distances are 1.509 Å for P-O_{terminal} and - 1.613 Å for P-O_{cont.} at the near-tetrahedral angles. The angles at the bridge oxygen atoms in P(1)-O(4)-P(2) and P(3)-O(11)-P(4) are 125.53° and 133.80°, respectively. Herewith, it should be noted that the lengths of P(4)-O(12) and P(4)-O(14) bonds have significantly increased. P(4) and Ni (1) polyhedra share common edge containing these atoms. It is evident that some increase in the length of bonds in P(1)-O(4)-P(2) fragment is due to the participation of oxygen in the coordination to Na(4) atom. There are channels filled with sodium atoms in the lattice framework of the structure. One of such channels running through the structure along the direction [100] contains Na(1) and Na(2) atoms surrounded by six atoms of oxygen.

The environment of Na(3) atom consists of irregular octagon with Na-O distances falling within 2.287-2.818 Å. Another atom of sodium is distributed in two positions, in the slightly smaller channel: Na(5) – in inversion centre and Na(4) – within the position of atom. The positions of Na(4) and Na(5) are partially disordered. Na(4) - Na(5) distance is 1.920 Å, Na(4) - Na(4') 2.843 Å. To maintain electrical neutrality, the filling degree of the latter is taken as 0.5.

Thermal tests of produced compounds have been performed with the derivatograph Q-1500 (Hungary). The sample was heated over the range of 20-1000° C under dynamic conditions of temperature elevation and using cylindrical platinum crucibles (weighed portion of compound was 0.300 g, heating rate – 5 degrees·min⁻¹). According to derivatographic data, phosphates are rather stable and flux at respective temperatures. When heated under dynamic conditions, the compounds loose no mass, which is also indicative of the presence of manganese (II) in the composition of double diphosphates.

The relation between conductivity and temperature has been established for some of the obtained compounds (Fig 4). During the analysis of data, it can be noted that the temperature of the change of conductivity pattern consistently grows for the number of phosphates, starting from Li₂MnP₂O₇ to K₂MnP₂O₇. This consistency can be attributed to significantly smaller lithium ion size comparing to sodium and potassium ions, and to the fact that its mobility within the lattice manifests at far lower temperatures. The mentioned above double phosphates of M₂MnP₂O₇-type are characterized by higher ionic conductivity, in particular Li₂MnP₂O₇ compound, and may be utilized in the development of functional materials.

Fig. 4. Dependence of conductivity on temperature for compounds:

1 – Li₂MnP₂O₇; 2 – Na₂MnP₂O₇; 3 – K₂MnP₂O₇

Conclusion. Single crystals of some double diphosphates have been identified in the fluxes of $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-Mn_2O_3-MF$ and $M^I_2O-P_2O_5-M^{II}O-MF$ phosphate systems (where, M^I – Li, Na; M^{II} – Mn, Ni, Co) for the first time. Physical and chemical research methods have been used to determine the regions of formation of phosphate compounds, study their properties, composition and lattice structures. XRD-technique has been employed to determine the structure of $Li_2MnP_2O_7$ and $Na_2NiP_2O_7$, and refine lattice parameters of double phosphates $Na_2MnP_2O_7$ and $Na_2CoP_2O_7$; the findings differ from the literature data. There have been selected optimum conditions and temperature ranges for the growing of large single crystals of 4 double diphosphates of alkali and bivalent metals. Their potential application as ionic conductors and as the basis for the development of functional materials has been demonstrated.

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